

Teacher Development Strategies for Problem-Based Learning at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Educational Service Area Office

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ABSTRACT: This research and development project purposes 1) to assess the current state, preferred conditions, and needs for problem-based learning at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Educational Service Area Office, 2) to develop strategies for enhancing teachers' capabilities in implementing problem-based learning at the school, 3) to apply the strategies to train teachers in problem-based learning, and 4) to evaluate the effectiveness of the teacher development strategies for problem-based learning at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Educational Service Area Office. The research sample consisted of 42 administrators and teachers from Namsuai Wittaya School, including 1 deputy principal and 41 teachers. The purposive sampling was used to select the sample. The data were collected using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire and interviews. The data analysis through frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and content analysis.

The results shown that;

1. The current state of problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, was at a moderate level overall ($\bar{x} = 3.14$, S.D. = 0.14). When considering each component from highest to lowest, it was found that conducting classroom research using problem-based learning innovations ($\bar{x} = 3.18$), supervision, follow-up, and development of teachers in the professional learning community ($\bar{x} = 3.17$), and competency-based learning management design ($\bar{x} = 3.12$) ranked highest. The desired state of problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, was at a very high level ($\bar{x} = 4.66$, S.D. = 0.12). When considering each component from highest to lowest, it was found that the assessment and evaluation of learning that empowers students based on real conditions ($\bar{x} = 4.75$), the creation of platforms and learning innovations ($\bar{x} = 4.74$), and competency-based learning management design ($\bar{x} = 4.65$) ranked highest. The analysis of the data shown that the average level of the current state was lower than that of the preferred state in all aspects.

2. The development of teachers in problem-based learning management prioritized the essential needs for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office. Overall, there were five main components; 1) competency-based learning management design, 2) creation of platforms and learning innovations, 3) assessment and evaluation of learning that empowers students based on real conditions, 4) supervision, follow-up, and development of teachers in the professional learning community, and 5) conducting classroom research using problem-based learning innovations.

3. The strategies for developing teachers in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, included a vision, 2 missions, 2 objectives, 2 strategic issues, 16 approaches, and 58 indicators.

4. The results of implementing the strategies for developing teachers in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, as observed by the administrators and teachers of Namsuai Wittaya School, indicated that the strategies have benefited the teachers, students, and the school. These strategies have provided new knowledge for efficient management, resulting in innovations in administration, both in the form of the teacher development strategy in problem-based learning management and the handbook for this strategy.

5. The results of the evaluation of the consistency of the teacher development strategy in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, show that overall, it was at a high level. The evaluation of the strategy in terms of overall appropriateness, feasibility, and benefits was at the highest level.

Keywords: Teacher Development Strategy, Problem-Based Learning Management

- Introduction**
- Research Framework**
- Research Objectives**
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1. Introduction

The current global society is an information society (Information Society), an era of technological advancement with changes in various area, for example, education, society, economy, and politics, as well as the Covid-19 pandemic. These changes have impacted development in all aspects of Thailand, particularly in communication and information exchange (Information and Communication Technology) via satellite systems. In the current Thai education system, it is an era of open learning with diverse forms and systems of education. Today's education ought to focus on developing students into well-rounded individuals in terms of physical, mental, intellectual, and abilities, with good morals and ethics. Prominently, all learners should be developed to possess 21st-century learning characteristics and skills through a learning process that emphasizes problem-solving, innovation creation, and providing multiple channels for accessing learning to help students learn to their full potential. This aligns with the era of learning, aiming to increase students' interest in becoming lifelong learners. Educational institutions would integrate modern technology to develop learning management models to keep up with the rapidly changing, borderless world of human imagination. Additionally, educational institutions must promote, support, prevent, assist, and resolve various issues that arise for students, who are the nation's valuable future resources (Sureemas Sukkasi and Patcharin Rujiranukul, 2019).

The key mission of educational institutions ought to develop curricula and proactive learning management processes. These should focus on enabling learners to learn in ways

that develop their abilities and experiences to their full potential. Additionally, they should improve the learning management of teachers to effectively achieve curriculum goals and foster learning behaviors in students that meet current curriculum objectives. This relies significantly on the collaboration of school personnel. If an educational institution has a systematic teaching and learning process, it will impact the quality of learners. Therefore, educational institutions should develop teachers to have knowledge and understanding of learner-centered learning management and understand processes that promote the natural and full potential development of learners (Nontawat Treenuntawan, 2017). Learner-centered learning management processes include organizing content and activities that align with the interests and aptitudes of learners while considering individual differences. It involves practicing skills, thinking processes, management, dealing with situations, and applying knowledge to prevent and solve problems. Activities should allow learners to gain real-life experience, practice, think critically, act effectively, and develop a continuous love of learning. Supporting teachers in creating a conducive environment, instructional media, and facilitating resources to foster learning is essential. Learning should occur at all times and places, involving parents and the community, and allowing learners to choose or decide on content that benefits them. Significantly, integrated learning should be organized, with teachers acting as facilitators and knowledge sources in learner-centered education. Administrators and teachers should design integrated learning plans that align with current conditions and 21st-century learning needs to develop teachers' skills and competencies in proactive learning management and students' 21st-century competencies (Phakdee Wongsanao, 2017).

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) was a teaching method that emphasizes having learners face real problem situations or scenarios. This method began with using problems to stimulate learners to research and seek knowledge from various sources to solve the problems. School administrators must prioritize the development of teachers as leaders in implementing problem-based learning in the learning process for students. This included developing skills in online learning management that was active learning, developing skills in designing blended or hybrid learning with diverse learning platforms, developing skills in designing learning that promotes knowledge-seeking and innovation creation, developing skills in using powerful questions that stimulate higher-order thinking, especially analytical and creative thinking, developing coaching skills to enhance student potential through both face-to-face and online learning, developing online learning resources that were suitable for the social and cultural context of the learners, developing skills in authentic assessment and evaluation that empowers students, developing skills in providing creative feedback, designing diverse learning experiences that responded to the nature and needs of individual learners, both in face-to-face and online learning, and designing a support system for learning assistance. Teachers could then use these skills to develop problem-based learning management for students, which would result in students creating knowledge and developing innovation skills, work skills, problem-solving skills, and learning independently (Wichai Wongyai and Marut Patthaphon, 2020).

Administrators had to exhibit strategic leadership, had a clear vision, and communicate effectively to foster new values in collaborative work. They ought to establish guidelines, processes, and methods for managing teachers in educational institutions to

ensure continuous teacher development in learning management. Strategies helped clearly defined future directions or core missions, aligning with the continuous internal and external changes within the organization. Developing strategies required a participatory process in organizational analysis (SWOT Analysis). It was the responsibility of administrators and teachers to determine strategies for the organization's operations to ensure competitiveness and survival in the future. Therefore, strategy formulation was crucial for school administrators to guide the organization in its operational strategies to remain competitive and sustainable in the future (Krit Suwanphrom, 2017).

Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, is a medium-sized school offering education from Grade 7 to Grade 12, following the Basic Education Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008). The academic performance summary for the 2019 academic year indicated that student achievement was below the set standards. Most teachers relied on traditional lecture-based teaching methods, focusing on the teacher as the central figure, and lacked knowledge and understanding of active learning planning and problem-based learning (PBL) activities. Consequently, student performance was unsatisfactory, consistent with the 2019 Self-Assessment Report (SAR) of Namsuai Wittaya School, which rated student quality at an acceptable level.

Given these reasons and the importance of the matter, the researcher was interested in studying strategies for developing teachers in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office. The goal was to identify guidelines, processes, and methods for teacher development in learning management, resulting in effective strategies for problem-based learning management that benefited both teachers and students, and to apply these strategies for efficient and effective teacher development in learning management.

2. Research Framework

In this study, the researcher has defined the research framework based on the conceptual frameworks established by Suriya Mas Sukkasit (2019) and Wisanee Jaichakarn (2017), as well as other scholars whose ideas were widely accepted. The framework also incorporated a review of relevant documents and previous research, along with the context related to this study.

From the theoretical components, the researcher has utilized criteria for selecting components that align with the research framework for this study. The framework consists of five components; 1) designing competency-based learning management, 2) creating platforms and innovations for learning, 3) measuring and evaluating learning outcomes in real-world contexts, 4) supervising, monitoring, and developing teachers within professional communities, and 5) conducting classroom research using problem-based learning innovations in Figure1:

Figure 1: Research Framework

3. Research Objectives

To study the current state and the preferred state of problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office

To develop strategies for teacher development and the implementation of these strategies in the development of teachers in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office

To apply the strategies for developing teachers in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office

To evaluate the strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office

4. Research Methodology

The research on Strategies for Teacher Development in Problem-Based Learning Management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, follows a Research & Development methodology. The researcher conducted the study in four phases as follows:

Phase 1: Studying the current state, the desired state, and the needs in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School. The methods included 1) reviewing relevant documents and research, and the components of teacher development in problem-based learning management, 2) studying the current state and the desired state of teacher development in problem-based learning management, 3) confirming the components of teacher development in problem-based learning management with five experts to assess the suitability and feasibility of the components of sustainable leadership of school administrators and, 4) analyzing data using mean and standard deviation statistics.

Phase 2: Developing strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School. The methods included 1) conducting meetings and PLCs with 42 participants, including the deputy director and 41 teachers at Namsuai Wittaya School, to analyze the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of teacher development in problem-based learning management, 2) drafting strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management, 3) interviewing five experts to review and improve the draft strategies, 5) analyzing qualitative data, and 6) creating a manual for using the strategies and assessing its suitability with five experts, using mean and standard deviation statistics.

Phase 3: Implementing the strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School. The methods included 1) applying the developed strategies with the administrators and teachers at Namsuai Wittaya School, 2)

interviewing seven administrators and department heads to gather feedback for further improvement of the strategies, and 3) analyzing documents related to teacher development in problem-based learning management, using mean and standard deviation statistics.

Phase 4: Evaluating the strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School. The methods included 1) developing a questionnaire based on the strategies from Phase 2, using a five-point Likert scale, and presenting it to advisors, 2) collecting data from the administrators and teachers at Namsuai Wittaya School, and 3) analyzing the data to assess the suitability, feasibility, and benefits of the strategies, using mean and standard deviation statistics.

5. Results

The results of the Development of Teacher Development Strategies for Problem-Based Learning Management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, revealed that:

The current state of problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, overall, is at a moderate level ($\bar{x} = 3.14$, S.D. = 0.14). When considering each component from highest to lowest, it was found that classroom research using problem-based learning innovation ($\bar{x} = 3.18$), supervision, follow-up, and teacher development in professional learning communities ($\bar{x} = 3.17$), and competency-based learning design ($\bar{x} = 3.12$) were the top three. The desired state of problem-based learning management, overall, was at the highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.66$, S.D. = 0.12). When considering each component from highest to lowest, it was found that authentic assessment and evaluation ($\bar{x} = 4.75$), creating platforms and learning innovations ($\bar{x} = 4.74$), and competency-based learning design ($\bar{x} = 4.65$) were the top three. The data analysis results indicated that the current state level was lower than the desired state level in all aspects.

The results of teacher development in problem-based learning management prioritized the needs for teacher development at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, with five main components; 1) competency-based learning design, 2) creating platforms and learning innovations, 3) authentic assessment and evaluation, 4) supervision, follow-up, and teacher development in professional learning communities, and classroom research using problem-based learning innovation.

The strategy for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School includes a vision, 2 missions, 2 goals, 2 strategic issues, 16 guidelines, and 58 indicators, as follows:

Vision: Developing students' potential to be competent and moral, leading the special economic development zone with management comparable to international standard schools by 2024.

Mission 1: Developing competency-based curriculum and learning management and curricula comparable to international standards.

Goal 1: Having a competency-based curriculum and learning management comparable to international standards.

Strategic Issue 1: Developing competency-based curriculum and learning management and curricula comparable to international standards, comprising:

Authentic assessment and evaluation, with 4 guidelines and 16 indicators.

Classroom research using problem-based learning innovation, with 4 guidelines and 18 indicators.

Competency-based learning design, with 3 guidelines and 17 indicators.

Mission 2: Developing teachers and staff to be professionals.

Goal 2: Teachers and staff are professionals.

Strategic Issue 2: Developing teachers and staff to be professionals, comprising:

Creating platforms and learning innovations, with 3 guidelines and 12 indicators.

Supervision, follow-up, and teacher development in professional learning communities, with 2 guidelines and 12 indicators.

The results of interviews on the implementation of strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School revealed that, prior to implementing the strategies, students' academic achievement in the 2019 academic year was below the set standard. Most teaching methods were lecture-based, adhering to traditional teacher-centered approaches, lacking knowledge and understanding of Active Learning plans and problem-based learning activities (PBL), leading to unsatisfactory student outcomes. This aligns with the 2019 Self-Assessment Report (SAR) of Namsuai Wittaya School, which rated student quality as "fair." After implementing the strategies for one academic year, interviews with administrators and department heads revealed improvements in teachers, students, and the school:

Teachers:

Acquired skills in designing problem-based learning processes.

Developed skills in creating platforms, media, and innovations for both online and onsite learning.

Improved skills in diverse authentic assessment and evaluation.

Received systematic supervision and applied feedback for self-development.

Engaged in continuous knowledge exchange, reflection, and lesson learned from learning management.

Used encountered problems in teaching to find new approaches or innovations.

Students:

1. Developed analytical thinking and problem-solving competencies.
2. Acquired technology skills and accessed learning anytime, anywhere.

3. Reached their full potential.
4. Experienced higher-quality learning management.
5. Received targeted problem-solving.

School:

1. Developed strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management.
2. Created a manual for using the strategies.
3. Established online classrooms for continuous learning.
4. Improved student achievement.
5. Implemented a quality educational management process.
6. Used local resources for learning management development.

Administrators played a crucial role in driving teacher development by setting visions, missions, goals, and strategies aligned with teacher development in learning management, including promoting authentic assessment, competency-based learning design, and supporting classroom research and continuous supervision.

The evaluation results of the alignment of the teacher development strategies for problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, overall, were at a high level. The evaluation of the strategies, overall, indicated the highest levels of suitability, feasibility, and benefits.

6. Discussions

The research findings on the strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning management at Namsuai Wittaya School, under the Nong Khai Secondary Education Service Area Office, include five strategies discussed as follows:

Strategy 1: Competency-Based Learning Design

This strategy is based on the analysis of strengths where school administrators have strong academic leadership. They promote and support teachers in designing learning processes that align with current situations by training them in competency-based learning design. Teachers collaborate to design and implement learning processes to equip students with 21st-century skills. Additionally, there is evaluation of competency-based learning management through supervision, reflection, lesson extraction, and knowledge exchange, leading to teacher self-development and enhanced competency-based learning design. This results in students achieving their full potential, aligning with the findings of Yupalai Malisorn and Kankana Ruangmontri (2020), who noted that schools should develop teachers' competencies in proactive learning management through workshops and internal supervision, focusing on designing learning, managing learning through thinking processes, and practical implementation, which helps improve teachers' learning process management and students' 21st-century skills.

Strategy 2: Creating Platforms and Learning Innovations

This strategy addresses weaknesses identified in the school's policy regarding media, technology, and innovation use. Teachers lack skills in creating media, platforms, and innovations that match current needs, leading to slow and ineffective learning for students. This strategy aims to strengthen the capabilities of administrators, teachers, and staff in using media, technology, and innovations effectively, enhancing students' learning efficiency. According to Wichai Wongyai and Marut Patthapol (2019), administrators should train teachers in using media, innovations, and technology in learning management, encouraging teachers to quickly adapt to online learning skills, develop hybrid learning methods with various platforms, and foster innovation through knowledge seeking.

Strategy 3: Authentic Assessment and Evaluation

This strategy addresses the weakness of inadequate personnel competency in authentic assessment and evaluation, focusing on assessment for decision-making. The existing methods do not align with current situations, resulting in students' lack of involvement in self-assessment and not meeting objectives, leading to inadequate self-development. This strategy promotes improving assessment and evaluation methods to enhance learning, creating quality assessment tools collaboratively. According to Achara Prasertsin (2020), administrators should promote competency-based assessment for 21st-century skills, focusing on learning assessments to diagnose learning issues, using progress assessments to raise self-awareness, and continuously designing learning for self-development.

Strategy 4: Supervision, Follow-Up, and Teacher Development in Professional Learning Communities (PLC)

This strategy capitalizes on the strength of school administrators in leadership aligned with the school's vision, mission, and goals. It involves systematic and clear internal supervision processes that are easy to implement, focusing on supervising and supporting problem-based learning management and participatory management through a teacher development project using a learning community. This strategy aims to strengthen the school's ability to continuously and effectively implement internal supervision and PLC processes. According to Tatsakorn Nochai (2016), internal school supervision supports teachers in researching, experimenting, and improving teaching methods, involving teachers in supervision planning, while Thongpan Panyaudomkul (2020) emphasizes using PLC processes to enhance teachers' quality in learning management, increasing specific skills and collaboration to improve student learning outcomes.

Strategy 5: Classroom Research Using Problem-Based Learning Innovation

This strategy addresses weaknesses in the school's implementation plan and workload related to research, where teacher research development is unclear and lacks supervision. Teachers lack skills in proper research, resulting in a lack of research outcomes for improving learning management. This strategy aims to strengthen the school's systematic and procedural approach to classroom research. According to Chanchai Thongsan (2016), administrators should develop teachers' knowledge and skills in classroom research to solve teaching problems according to procedures, including problem

survey and analysis, solution methods, innovation development, implementation, result summarization, and report writing, using strategies like workshops and supervision.

7. Recommendations

Suggestions for Applying Research Findings

Educational Service Area Offices

The findings from this research can be used to inform decision-making in planning, policy-setting, and developing strategies and approaches to promote and enhance teachers' capabilities in managing learning to ensure effectiveness and efficiency in alignment with current needs.

School Administrators

School leaders can use the strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning, derived from this research, as guidelines for implementing problem-based learning management within their schools. This will help in developing and promoting more effective and efficient learning management practices.

Educational Supervisors

Supervisors responsible for curriculum development and learning processes can apply the strategies for teacher development in problem-based learning from this research to guide their supervision, monitoring, and evaluation of learning management processes in schools or to formulate strategies accordingly.

Suggestions for Future Research

Development of Teacher Development Models

Future studies should focus on developing models for teacher development in problem-based learning specific to schools under the jurisdiction of the Nong Khai Secondary Educational Service Area Office.

Customized Research and Strategy Development

Each educational institution should conduct research and develop strategies tailored to their own context to ensure alignment with their unique environment and to benefit their specific school.

Research Based on School Size

Research should be conducted and strategies should be developed for schools based on their size—small, medium, and large—to align with the context of each institution.

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